

Formation of Moral Self-Consciousness in Adolescents in the Process of Psychological Counselling

Iuliia ALIEKSIEIEVA¹,
Nelia BIHUN²,
Inna CHUKHRII³,
Halyna HONCHAROVSKA⁴,
Svitlana KALISHCHUK⁵,
Dariia OTYCH⁶

¹National Pedagogical Dragomanov University, Ukraine, yulya-alekseeva-74@ukr.net

²National Pedagogical Dragomanov University, Ukraine, nelabigun@gmail.com

³Vinnitsia Mykhailo Kotsiubynsky State Pedagogical University, Ukraine, chukhriinna@gmail.com

⁴Ternopil Volodymyr Hnatiuk National Pedagogical University, Ukraine, ggalina.tnpu@gmail.com

⁵Borys Grinchenko Kyiv University, Ukraine, klana@ukr.net

⁶National Pedagogical Dragomanov University, Ukraine, otychdd@ukr.net

Abstract: *The article reveals issues related to formation of moral self-awareness in the process of psychological counselling. The meaning of the concepts: “consciousness”, “moral”, “moral self-awareness”, “counselling”, “psychology”, “psychological counselling” is clarified. A classification of psychological counselling is presented. A review of literature by domestic and foreign researchers on fostering moral self-awareness in adolescents is made. It is investigated that the American psychologist Hall (1904) first covered the issue of formation of moral self-consciousness in adolescents. It is determined that the functions of moral self-consciousness include self-control, self-perception, self-approval, self-understanding, self-improvement. It is found that scientists distinguish 2 types of self-awareness: subjective and objective. It is emphasized that self-awareness is the ability to clearly and realistically evaluate one’s behavior. The moral self-consciousness of adolescents with high, medium and low levels of self-esteem is considered. In addition, emphasis is placed on the fact that moral traits are the factors that shape a person. It has been found that moral self-awareness is based on the following factors: cognitive, emotional and behavioral. It is noted that the ability to communicate plays an important role in formation of moral self-awareness. The signs that prompt a teenager think about visiting a psychologist have been identified. It is proved that knowledge about one’s strengths in moral self-awareness helps adolescents to form their own moral well-being. It is found that conducting simulation games by a psychologist during a group training allows a specialist to determine the level of moral self-awareness of an adolescent, as well as to form strong moral virtues. It is proved that a game helps to conduct an effective psychological counselling, because a child feels comfortable, relaxed, openly shares thoughts and feelings. A remote form of psychological counseling is considered. It is emphasized that a psychologist works with a teenager, as well as with his/her parents. It was found that psychological counseling comprises a diagnostic and a therapeutic part.*

Keywords: *Consciousness, moral, moral self-awareness, counselling, psychology, psychological counselling.*

How to cite: Alieksieieva, I., Bihun, N., Chukhrii, I., Honcharovska, H., Kalishchuk, S., & Otych, D. (2022). Formation of Moral Self-Consciousness in Adolescents in the Process of Psychological Counselling. *BRAIN. Broad Research in Artificial Intelligence and Neuroscience*, 13(1Sup1), 207-219. <https://doi.org/10.18662/brain/13.1Sup1/313>

Introduction

At present, in the rapid pace of development of socio-political and economic events (Florea, 2017), there is a marked decrease in the importance of moral and ethical norms in society, which are indicators of behaviour. It is known that adolescents have a growing need for self-affirmation, self-regulation, self-confidence. Adolescence is the age of special development of a teenager (Demchenko et al., 2021; Komogorova et al., 2021; Kosholap et al., 2021). Moral principles, norms are indicators of the inner state of an adolescent. In addition, sometimes young people show manifestations of low levels of moral values, selfishness.

So, to begin with, the following concepts need to be clarified: “consciousness”, “moral”, “moral self-awareness”, “counselling”, “psychology”, “psychological counselling”.

In the Dictionary of the Ukrainian language edited by Bilodid (1978) there is a definition of the concept “consciousness is the process of reflecting reality by the human brain, which covers all forms of mental activity and determines a purposeful human activity”.

From the dictionary edited by Hornostay (2001), we learn that “self-awareness is the ability of a person to reflect oneself, to perceive oneself from the outside, to reflect on one’s capabilities for successful formation, development and improvement of personality”.

From the Encyclopaedia of Modern Ukraine by Abolin (2019), we learn that “moral is a spiritual and an ethic factor that regulates human behaviour and contains generalized norms, values, patterns of behaviour, principles of attitude to other people”.

According to Zimyansky (2015), “moral is a way of organizing life relationships that requires adolescents to independently analyse their actions, behaviour, etc., based on the formed moral consciousness”.

According to Shkilna (2014), “moral self-awareness is a person’s awareness of himself, his own moral qualities, behaviour, actions, motives, attitude to the world around, one’s activities for oneself and society”.

According to Osadko (2005), “counselling is the activity of a consultant aimed at providing services in the form of discussing issues raised for organizations and individuals”.

From Dictionary of Foreign Words by Lukyanyuk (2001-2021) we learn that “psychology is a science that studies patterns, development and forms of mental activity of living beings”.

A review of the literature by domestic authors Tsymbaliuk (2005), Tsilmak (2020) suggests that psychological science has many options for interpreting the essence of “psychological counselling”.

According to Tsymbaliuk (2005), “psychological counselling is a conversation between a person and a psychologist who tries to help solve their problems and establish interpersonal relationships”.

Tsilmak (2020) provides a classification of psychological counselling: individual and group, one-time and multiple; on personal request and without it. Consultations can be with additional testing, with the involvement of methods of psychological correction. By duration: one-time consultation, which lasts 45-60 minutes, short-term consultation - for 3-4 sessions, medium-term - 10-15 sessions, long-term, lasts during a year. It can also be a face-to-face or a remote counselling. During a meeting, a psychologist listens to the client, tries to help alleviate the emotional state, helps to solve the problem.

Review of literature by domestic and foreign researchers on fostering moral self-awareness in adolescents

The first studies on formation of moral self-awareness in adolescents belong to American psychologist and educator Hall (1904). The scientist created the first psychology laboratory, started a journal on psychology, introduced the concept of a “psychological test”, wrote books on the study of children’s mind, taught in detail the development of the child in adolescence. In addition, the American psychologist founded the American Psychological Association, and therefore became its first president. In addition, he organized and edited other periodicals related to psychology: “Journal of Genetic Psychology” (then called “The Pedagogical Seminary”), “The Journal of Religious Psychology”, “The Journal of Applied Psychology”. It is worth noting that Hall (1904) emphasized that educational institutions should pay more attention to the upbringing of children rather than to the teaching of subjects (Watson, 2018).

The issues of the state of moral self-consciousness in adolescents in the process of psychological counselling was covered in the dissertation abstract by Aliksieieva (2006). The author emphasized that during psychological counselling, psychologist should pay attention to both personal and interpersonal problems that cause problems of moral self-awareness. The researchers conducted a planned experiment, which revealed that during the period of psychological counselling there was an

improvement in the ability of adolescents to self-analysis, compassion, empathy; the level of moral self-awareness increased.

Research on fostering moral self-awareness in older adolescents was covered by Shkilna (2014), who noted the functions of moral self-awareness: self-knowledge, self-perception, self-approval, moral self-esteem, evaluation of other people's actions, moral reflection, self-control, self-improvement.

It is worth to note Miller's work (2021), which states that "self-awareness" is a focus on oneself. The author distinguishes between 2 types: subjective and objective. The subjective type is the interpretation of the fact that we are the result of our ideas, aspirations and, certainly, behaviour. The idea of objective consciousness resides in the fact that we compare ourselves with others, subordinate our actions to the standard of correct behaviour. A person feels restlessness, irritability when evaluating one's "self" with the ideas of the ideal. Objective self-awareness is achieved when a person can exercise self-regulation, i.e., the ability to control one's actions and thoughts. Obviously, if a person focuses on oneself, the person is aware of oneself. The author also singles out 7 examples of the theory of self-awareness: actions at the moment, attitude to actions; emotions at that moment; appearance; internal conflicts, beliefs and values; attitudes of other people; your vision of how others perceive you. Miller (2021) gives 7 tips for improving self-awareness skills: 1) learn to meditate; 2) seek feedback, 3) learn to write down, analyse actions; 4) use assessments of personality and character traits; 5) keep a journal; 6) write morning pages; 7) learn to replace negative beliefs with healthy ones that promote emotional well-being.

From the work of Ackerman (2021) it becomes known that self-awareness is the ability to clearly, realistically evaluate one's behaviour, actions, to analyse them honestly. In addition, the author highlights the benefits of self-awareness:

- affects our activity, stimulates positive self-development and perception;
- promotes creative and productive work, helps to exercise self-control and feel pleasure from what has been done;
- easy to make decisions;
- improves communicative competence and increases self-confidence.

In the article, Dowden (2014) advises counsellors to practice counselling in "stress-free zones", having a conversation with the client, meditating and organizing physical activity. The author proposes a 3-step model to improve self-awareness, each of the strategies is focused on improving cognitive, emotional and behavioral processes.

The article Sandu (2014) focuses on formation of moral self-awareness. The author argues that adolescents' moral self-awareness consists of what they think, feel, and behave. Certainly, formation of moral consciousness is influenced by the family, school and community, as well as the social, cultural, historical and economic spheres. The "self" personality is a structure that contains one's own perceptions and values, as well as the views and influence of family members and society. Formation of adolescent self-awareness usually occurs from the fact that boys and girls, forming their personality, contemplate, compare themselves with their peers. Adolescents with low self-esteem may have a good appearance, but because of pessimistic attitude to life see the negative side in everything. Often, low self-esteem in adolescents leads to nutritional disorders, suicidal thoughts, consumption of psychotropic substances, early sexual life, which are the major health problems. Obviously, teenagers who have high self-esteem are interested, self-confident, because they believe that they have everything for successful learning. They do not feel tension and have no internal conflicts. It is clear that people with high self-esteem are easy to mobilize, they are independent, successful, because they know how to interpret situations from a different perspective. People with low self-esteem are dissatisfied with themselves, are afraid of new tasks, try to avoid responsibility, feel rejected, they do not like the consequences of their activities, they do not try to get into conflicts, because they feel it is better for them to be unnoticed. Certainly, formation of high and low self-esteem comes from the family, because it is in the family that the child experiences "lessons of happiness or unhappiness".

In her article Ternopilka (2014) considers the essence of moral self-consciousness of an individual, emphasizes the age characteristics of adolescents.

The transition from childhood to adolescence is characterized by increased attention to relationships with peers. Moreover, adolescents show symptoms of depression. Fear and self-criticism may be associated with nutritional disorders, psychosis, and substance abuse (Gilbert, 2008).

In her article Moreira (2018) explores relationship between self-awareness, empathy, individualization, and moral issues. The author argues that moral traits are the factors that shape a person as he/she is.

It is worth noting a significant contribution of the scientist Bulakh (2004) on formation of moral consciousness of adolescents. The domestic researcher made a review of the literature by various authors on moral self-awareness of adolescents. She developed her own concept that helps to form and improve moral self-awareness of adolescents: identified the origin,

revealed the content and the structure of moral education and proved that formation of moral self-awareness is based on the following factors: cognitive, emotional and behavioral.

In his research Zymianskyi (2015) notes that moral self-awareness affects motivation, self-esteem, choice of goals and means to achieve them. In its essence, self-consciousness and moral consciousness contain a moral idea of good and evil, truth and falsehood, moral virtues, ideals and principles that make sense in the unity of one's own self and a particular other person. According to the author, cognitive development is characterized by development of abstract thinking, logical memory. Therefore, these factors affect thoughts, views, moral values of the adolescent. The emotional sphere is characterized by high emotional excitability, emotional experiences, fear, anxiety. Furthermore, adolescents can set a goal and with the help of perseverance, stubbornness, the ability to overcome difficulties achieve the goal. The ability to communicate plays an important role in formation of the adolescent's moral self-consciousness, because with the help of communication an adolescent can establish a relationship of equality, play the role of organizer and performer. And, certainly, for adolescence the main thing is formation of one's self.

Thus, in adolescence appear psychological prerequisites for emergence, formation of moral self-awareness: cognitive, emotional, volitional, motivational-emotional, social activity, interpersonal communication, the need to grow up as soon as possible, a new level of self-awareness.

Effective organization of psychological counselling is a step towards a successful formation of moral self-awareness

Adolescence is difficult not only for the child but also for parents, so a consultation with a psychologist can be useful. A specialist can listen to a teenager, support them and provide qualified advice; furthermore, explain to the parents the reasons for a particular behaviour of the child. What signs in the behaviour of an adolescent can prompt a child and parents to visit a psychologist? If a child has no motivation to learn, does not want to learn and, moreover, does not listen to anyone, feels tired for a long time, indifference to everything, has signs of depression; irritability, anxiety and aggression are felt in conversation; a teenager tries to avoid talking to adults or peers because it is difficult for them to find a common language.

An important aspect of the adolescent's moral consciousness is the moral position, i.e., observance of moral norms and a stable set of awareness through a system of guidelines and motives by which it is guided. A formed

moral position is one of the criteria that proves a high or a medium level of moral formation.

Matthews M. (2018), a professor of engineering psychology at the US Military Academy, shares his experience in conducting practical classes with teenagers. The author conducted a seminar for adolescents whose parents serve in the Army. Therefore, children often have to adapt to a new environment: school staff, teachers, make new friends. The purpose of this meeting was to develop adolescents' self-awareness of their positive qualities, as well as to demonstrate how the strengths of an individual can help to achieve success. The author used a questionnaire that helps to measure 24 strengths of character, organized into 6 main moral virtues: wisdom and knowledge, courage, humanity, justice, moderation, transcendence. The professor conducted work with adolescents in the form of a training: he divided 30 children into 6 groups who worked separately at the table. The task for teenagers was to name 5 strongest qualities of character, then gave 5 minutes in order for participants to recall from their own experience how one of their strong character traits helped them succeed. The teenagers shared their impressions during the discussion in their group, and then one representative presented the conclusion to the general audience. In the second practical part, the coach assigned 6 virtues to the team members, presented a life situation that needed to be solved using one of the virtues. Thus, knowledge one's strengths helps adolescents to form their own moral well-being.

In her publication Dr. Bajovic & Rizzo (2020) presents theoretical views of researchers who worked and proved the theory of cognitive development and social development. The author argues that adolescents' lack of understanding of their own moral thinking and moral emotions is a key reason that prevents them from making correct decisions. With the help of meta-moral cognitive strategies, teachers will help adolescents to develop moral thinking, control actions and control their own emotions.

In his article, Prutchenko (2000) believes that imitation games are effective for formation of moral consciousness in adolescents, which aim to: study the level of development of moral self-awareness, as well as to form strong moral virtues. For this game, a speaker is chosen in the team of teenagers: an adult who sells moral values, and high school students buy them. In addition, there are some independent experts in this game. Children buy, choosing values, and explain how the acquired positive values can become a real asset. During the game, teenagers demonstrate their own ability to make choices, make decisions, the ability to communicate, the ability to be independent, to prove their point, to adhere to moral values. An

interesting form of activity for teenagers is working on a project –an “auction of creative ideas”. During this work, adolescents study the necessary literature and prove the appropriateness of the choice.

Alias (2019) emphasizes that the concept of self-awareness helps people solve psychological problems and improve their health. The author emphasizes that self-awareness is an understanding of the inner state. The researcher notes that clients may not always be able to trust their problems during group counselling. Therefore, self-disclosure is a process of communication when a person is ready to entrust his/her problems to another person. It has been proven that during an organized game it becomes easier for clients to complete the task. Thus, the research proves that the game is effective for psychological counselling: a client feels comfortable and thus self-disclosure occurs.

Adolescence is a bio-psycho-social period between childhood to adulthood. Therefore, during this period, boys and girls should be aware of their thoughts, values, actions, etc. In order to do this, they should understand what self-awareness is. As it is known, according to Kalaiyaranan (2017), “self-awareness is a person’s ability to introspect, to recognize their “self” as a personality different from others. If a child is not aware of his/her “self”, it negatively affects the development. The author presents the results of the study among adolescents conducted in India on how psychological intervention affects self-awareness of adolescents. To determine the level of self-awareness, adolescents were offered testing before and after counselling. The training consisted of 3 parts and was conducted for a group of 30 people. The lesson included group activities, an information message and a “brainstorming” exercise (focusing on self-awareness). Before starting counseling, only 53.3% of adolescents had an average level of moral self-awareness, and 23.3% had a high and low level each. After the training, the test results showed that 73.3% of adolescents had a high level of self-awareness, 26.7% - an average. Therefore, psychological counseling proved effective for adolescents.

The specifics of remote psychological counselling on the Internet were analysed by Mytsko (2011), who identified the activities of online counselling psychologists, which include assisting the client in resolving conflicts in family or in team; help the client to find himself; support the client so that he/she can overcome the crisis situation. Among the positive features of Internet counselling is the rapid finding of the site, a sense of comfort and economic convenience. In addition, in e-mail communication, clients rarely think about literacy, so they feel emotionally liberated.

It is worth noting that Tsybaliuk (2005) emphasizes that the success of counselling, certainly, depends on the competencies: his ability to listen to the client, understand the situation and communicate successfully. In addition, mental counselling includes psychological correction and psychotherapy. Moreover, counselling is aimed at a productive conversation that can help a person solve psychological problems.

Surely, a psychologist should inform the parents of an adolescent about the specific signs of the child's development, as well as to predict future manifestations of behaviour. Although the materials that are covered by parents should protect interests of children. Psychological research should be accurate, specific, carry truthful information, describe the strengths and weaknesses of an adolescent. In counselling parents, the psychologist should focus on the causes, consequences and ways to overcome conflict with peers.

Adolescents develop dynamically, so psychological counselling should have its own specifics, which is tailored to a certain individual. In the course of training the psychologist usually carries out two main tasks: diagnostic and therapeutic. During the diagnosis, the specialist tries to understand the situation of the teenager, which prompted him to consult a specialist, as well as to find out the range of factors that led to the situation. Regarding the implementation of therapy, the psychologist selects contemporary techniques, methods of conducting that calm the teenager, stabilize the emotional state, provide psychological support, as well as activate the own resources of the adolescent child to overcome the problem. During this activity, the psychologist should adhere to responsibility, confidentiality, be able to establish a contact of trust with the child, so that the teenager could tell true details of the situation.

Conclusion

Therefore, the article reveals the issue of formation of moral self-awareness in the process of psychological counselling. The meaning of the concepts: "consciousness", "morality", "moral self-awareness", "counselling", "psychology", "psychological counselling" is clarified. In addition, a classification of psychological counselling is provided.

A review of the literature by domestic and foreign researchers on fostering moral self-awareness in adolescents enables to state that the American psychologist and educator G. Stanley Hall was the first to cover the issue of formation of moral self-awareness in adolescents.

It is known that the functions of moral self-awareness include self-control, self-perception, self-approval, self-knowledge, self-improvement. It was found out that scientists identify 2 types of self-awareness: subjective and objective. Obviously, self-awareness is the ability to clearly and realistically evaluate one's behavior.

The paper considers moral self-awareness of adolescents with high, medium and low levels of self-esteem. In addition, emphasis is placed on the fact that moral traits are the factors that shape a person. It has been found that moral self-awareness is based on the following factors: cognitive, emotional and behavioral. It should be noted that the ability to communicate plays an important role in formation of moral self-awareness.

The signs that prompt a teenager think about visiting a psychologist have been identified. It is proved that knowledge about strengths of moral self-awareness helps adolescents to form their own moral well-being. Conducting simulation games by a psychologist during a group training allows the specialist to determine the level of moral self-awareness of an adolescent, as well as to form strong moral virtues. It is proven that a game helps to conduct an effective psychological consultation, because the child feels comfortable, relaxed, openly shares thoughts and feelings. In addition, there is a remote form of psychological counseling. It is emphasized that the psychologist works with a teenager, as well as with his/her parents. It was found that psychological counseling contains a diagnostic and a therapeutic component.

References

- Abolin, T. H., & Nadolnyi, I. F. (2019). Entsyklopediia suchasnoi Ukrainy [Encyclopedia of modern Ukraine].
https://esu.com.ua/search_articles.php?id=69220
- Ackerman, C. E. (2021). What is self-awareness and why is it important? [+5 ways to increase it]. *Positive Psychology*.
- Alias, N. F., Mustafa, S. M. S., & Ahmad, Z. (2019). Investigating the usefulness of counselling tool to improve students' self-awareness. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 9(13), 166–172.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.6007/IJARBS/v9-i13/6252>
- Aliexsieieva, Yu. A. (2006). *Stanovlennia moralnoi samovidomosti pidlitkiv u protsesi psykholohichnoho konsultuvannia* [Formation of moral self-consciousness of teenagers in the process of psychological counseling]. National Pedagogical Dragomanov University.
- Bajovic, M., & Rizzo, K. (2020). Meta-moral cognition: bridging the gap among adolescents' moral thinking, moral emotions and moral actions. *International*

- Journal of Adolescence and Youth*, 13, 1–11.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/02673843.2020.1867206>
- Bilodid, I. K., Buriachok, A. A., Hnatiuk, H. M., & Dotsenko, P. P. (1978). *Slovník ukraïnskoi mowy* [Dictionary of the Ukrainian language]. Vol. 9, 77. Naukovadumka.
- Bulakh, I. S. (2004). *Psykhobolohichni osnovy osobystisnogo zrostannia pidlitkiv* [Psychological bases of personal growth of teenagers]. (PhDthesis). National Pedagogical Dragomanov University.
- Demchenko, I., Maksymchuk, B., Bilan, V., Maksymchuk, I., & Kalynovska, I. (2021). Training Future Physical Education Teachers for Professional Activities under the Conditions of Inclusive Education. *BR/AIN. Broad Research in Artificial Intelligence and Neuroscience*, 12(3), 191-213.
<https://doi.org/10.18662/brain/12.3/227>
- Dowden, A., Warren, J., & Kambui, H. (2014). Three-tiered model toward improved self-awareness and self-care. *Ideas and Research You Can Use: VISTAS*, 1, 1–9. <https://docplayer.net/8354114-Three-tiered-model-toward-improved-self-awareness-and-self-care.html>
- Florea, D. (2017). *Principalele contracte de comerț internațional*. Lumen.
- Gilbert, P. C., & Gilbert, P. (2008). Irons shame, self-criticism, and self-compassion in adolescence. *Adolescent Emotional Development and the Emergence of Depressive D*. https://self-compassion.org/wp-content/uploads/2016/06/Gilbert_Irons_2009.pdf.
- Hall, G. S. (1904). *Adolescence its psychology and its relations to physiology, anthropology, sociology sex, crime, religion and education*. Appleton and Company.
- Hornostai, P. P., Tytarenko, T. M., & Hrabaskaia, Y. A. (2001). *Psykholohiia osobystosti* [Personality psychology]. Ruta.
- Kalaiyaran, M., & Daniel, S. (2017). Effectiveness of Psychological Intervention on Self-Awareness of Adolescents. *Effectiveness of Psychological Intervention on Self-Awareness of Adolescents*, 7, 28–32. <http://www.iosrjournals.org/iosr-jhss/papers/Conf.17004/Volume-4/7.%2028-32.pdf>
- Komogorova, M., Maksymchuk, B., Bernatska, O., Lukianchuk, S., Gerasymova, I., Popova, O., Matviichuk, T., Solovyov, V., Kalashnik, N., Davydenko, H., Stoliarenko, O., Stoliarenko, O., & Maksymchuk, I. (2021). Pedagogical Consolidation of Pupil-Athletes Knowledge of Humanities. *Revista Romaneasca Pentru Educatie Multidimensionala*, 13(1), 168 - 187.
<https://doi.org/10.18662/rrem/13.1/367>
- Kosholap, A., Maksymchuk, B., Branitska, T., Martynets, L., Boichenko, A., Stoliarenko, O., Matsuk, L., Surovov, O., Stoliarenko, O., & Maksymchuk, I. (2021). Neuropsychological Bases of Self-Improvement of Own Physical Health of Future Teachers in the Course of University Education. *BR/AIN*.

- Broad Research in Artificial Intelligence and Neuroscience*, 12(3), 171-190.
<https://doi.org/10.18662/brain/12.3/226>
- Lukyanyuk, V. (2021). Psykholohiia [Psychology]. Slovnyk in shomovnykh sliv [Dictionary of foreign words]. <https://www.jnsm.com.ua/cgi-bin/u/book/sis.pl?Qry=%CF%F1%E8%F5%EE%EB%EE%E3%B3%FF>
- Matthews, M. D. (2018). *Nurturing Character Self-Awareness in Teens*. Psychology Today.
- Miller, K. D. (2021). Using Self-Awareness Theory and Skill in Psychology. Positive Psychology.
- Moreira, L., DeSouza, M., & Guerra, V. (2018). Self-Perception, Empathy and Moral Self-Concept Predict Moral Concerns in Adults. *Social Psychology*, 28. <https://doi.org/10.1590/1982-4327e2818>
- Mytsko, V. M. (2011). Spetsyfyka dystantsiinoho psykholohichnoho konsultuvannia v merezhi Internet [Specifics of remote psychological counseling on the Internet Scientific, 1]. *Naukovyi visnyk Lvivskoho derzhavnogo universytetu vnutrishnikh sprav* [Bulletin of Lviv State University of Internal Affairs], 1, 68–80. https://www.lvduvs.edu.ua/documents_pdf/visnyky/nvsp/01_2011/11mvmvmi.pdf
- Osadko, O. Yu. (2005). *Tekhnolohii psykholohichnoho konsultuvannia* [Technologies of psychological counseling]. Redaktsiia zahalnopedahohichnykh hazet.
- Prutchenko, A. S. (2000). Shkola zhyttia: metodychni rozrobky sotsialno-psykholohichnykh treninhiv [School of life: methodical developments of social and psychological trainings]. *MOOD i M "Nova tsyvilizatsiia"*.
- Sandu, C., Panișoara, G., & Panișoara, I. (2014). Study on the development of self-awareness in teenagers. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 180, 1656–1660. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2015.05.060>
- Shkilna, I. M. (2014). *Vykhovannia moralnoi samosvidomosti starshykh pidlitkiv yak naukova problema* [Education of moral self-consciousness of older adolescents as a scientific problem]. Kyiv.
- Ternopil'ska, V. I. (2014). Moralna samosvidomist starshoklasnyka (zahalna kharakterystyka ta osoblyvosti formuvannia). Naukove elektronne vydannia "Osvitolohichniy dyskurs" [Scientific electronic publication "Educational Discourse"], 4, 1–10. [https://elibrary.kubg.edu.ua/id/eprint/7027/1/V_Ternopil'ska_NEVOD_4\(8\)_GI.pdf](https://elibrary.kubg.edu.ua/id/eprint/7027/1/V_Ternopil'ska_NEVOD_4(8)_GI.pdf).
- Tsil'mak, O. M. (2020). *Psykholohichne konsultuvannia* [Psychological counseling]. (Master's thesis abstract). Odessa.
- Tsymbaliuk, I. M. (2005). *Psykholohichne konsultuvannia ta korektsiia. Modulno-rei'tynbovyi kurs: Navchalnyi posibnyk* [Psychological counseling and correction. Modular rating course: Textbook]. VD "Profesional".

Watson, R. I., & Hall, G. (2018). *Stanley works by Hall supplementary bibliography*.
Encyclopedia Com.

Zymianskyi, A. R. (2015). *Psykhobichni umovy rozvytku moralnoi samosvidomosti pidlitkiv*
[Psychological conditions for the development of moral self-awareness of
adolescents] [Master's thesis abstract]. Drohobych State Pedagogical
University named after Ivan Franko.